

Invariance of light speed and of interference in Michelson-Morley experiment based on the hypothesis of the physical vacuum as a fluid made of "Immaterial Atom" bosons

Abstract

In the hypothesis of the physical vacuum as a fluid medium made of "Immaterial Atom" bosons (Ref. 1, 2), IA, we can explain the invariance of the speed of light and of the interference in Michelson-Morley experiment.

Introduction

The pair generation mechanism described in Ref.1 and Ref.2 is only one among the possible conceivable options considering the physical vacuum as a fluid made of IA bosons. IA bosons, as qubit operators (Ref.3), can be overlapped. At least within certain energy limits, these even partial overlaps of mutually null electric fields can justify the initial assumptions of continuity of the fluid medium (Ref.1, 2). Regarding wave transmission the momentum of the photon is given by $p=h/\lambda=E/c$, from which

$$c = E / p \quad (1)$$

where

h =Planck's constant

λ =length of the electromagnetic wave that transits through the IA bosons, polarizing them as it passes (Ref. 1, 2)

E = energy transported by the polarizing electromagnetic wave and possessed by the IA during wave transition

c =light speed.

For the IA bosons, according to Ref. 1, we apply the formulas

$$p * X = \pm h\Delta \quad (2)$$

and

$$E * t = \pm h\Delta \quad (3)$$

in which $0 \leq \Delta \leq 1$, where

$$\Delta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4}{h^2 c^2}} \quad (4)$$

is now called “masking” factor (Ref.1, 2). $|Q_e|=1,6022E-19C$ is the virtual electric charge of electron or positron, which is affected by the “masking” effect (Ref. 1). k_0 is Coulomb’s electrostatic constant. The value of Δ is indeterminable.

X is the significant radial size that mathematically describes the distribution of the overlapped charges or, equivalently, of their mutually null electric fields (Ref.1, 2). t is the equivalent rotation period of the IA around its spin axis. Associated with the equivalent rotation period t is the angular speed $\omega=2\pi/t$. By equivalent rotation of the IA boson, conditioned by the electromagnetic wave that transits through it at the speed of light, is to be understood the theoretical rotation of the boson around its spin axis, with its peripheral speed $c = \omega * X$ equal to the light speed and with a period t equal to the time the wave in all its length needs to be transmitted through it. **t represents the unit of time and indicates how fast time flows.** According to (3) it depends on the energy possessed by the IA. It is also related to the oscillation of the two virtual fermions that make it up (Ref. 1, 2). The frequency of the wave coincides with the oscillation frequency of the two virtual fermions. IA bosons are identifiable as the virtual particles that convey wave propagation, which occurs by transmitting a temporary polarization at the speed of light between an IA boson and the next adjacent one and so on (Note A). Among the possible paths the wave follows a preferential one. Its passage involves a state of oscillation due to the distancing of the two IA’s virtual charges that remain partially overlapped (Note B). Distancing ends once the wave has passed and the stable unperturbed equilibrium condition is restored (Note C) (Ref.1, 2). (2) and (3) indicate that IAs are characterized by physical quantities that vary in a continuous way. Variations, in general, are conditioned by any factor that affects their energy state (Ref. 1, 2). In particular, they are conditioned by the passage of electromagnetic waves and by the space-time curvature, also according to what is described about the birth of the gravitational field (Ref. 1). Compared with the stable unperturbed equilibrium condition (Ref. 1, 2), the value of these quantities may show positive or negative variations, summarized by the $E = E_0 \pm \delta E, t = t_0 \pm \delta t, p = p_0 \pm \delta p, X = X_0 \pm \delta X$.

When $\Delta=1$ the IA boson is in the stable unperturbed equilibrium condition, in which X can assume very large values, hypothetically even thousands of km (Ref. 2). From (4) derives that $Q_e = 0$. It means that in this situation the electric field of the virtual fermion is totally masked by the other. The quantum of action h , with dimension $[J*s]$, is totally possessed by the boson.

When $0 < \Delta < 1$, one or more waves freely propagate through the transmission of the polarization of the IA bosons. In the portion of IA boson directly polarized by the wave the polarization is transmitted at the speed c of the electromagnetic wave. On the remaining portion we cannot say anything deterministic (Ref. 1). When Δ tends from 1 to 0 decreases the action possessed by the boson and increases the action of the individual virtual fermions that are unmasking. Their total amount is always h . The momentum less depends on the equivalent rotation of the boson and more on the motion of the charges, whose electric fields are more and more distancing and distinguishing as the oscillation amplitude increase (Ref. 1). (2) and (3) consider the equivalent rotation of the boson and not the motion of the particles that are developing. The equivalent rotation describes the behaviour of the IA boson, not of the virtual or real fermions. The value of Δ tells us how much the action h acts in a bosonic or fermionic way.

When $\Delta=0$ we are in the “ultimate equilibrium” condition, reached by the energy of two incident waves at the ultimate equilibrium frequency $f_* = 1,0638E+23$ 1/s (Ref.1, 2) (Note D). In this unstable equilibrium transition situation ends the bosonic physics and begins the fermionic one (Ref. 1, 2). From this situation the electric fields either return to the IA boson condition or they completely separate. In this case they can't convey the electromagnetic waves anymore and the real particles take place, each with the known amount of energy $E = 0,511\text{MeV}$ (Ref. 1, 2). The quantum of action h , initially possessed by the IA boson, will be now divided between the two fermions (Ref. 1, 2).

Methods

From (1), (2) and (3) it follows that

$$c = X/t \quad (5)$$

in which X depends on the energy or momentum possessed by the boson according to (2) and (3) and the equivalent rotation period t remains automatically conditioned. Therefore (5) **defines the light speed as the significant size and the equivalent rotation period of the IA vary**, depending on the energy it possesses. In this case energy is conditioned by the passage of the polarizing electromagnetic wave (Ref. 1,2). **The variations of significant size and equivalent rotation period will be in such a ratio as to always guarantee the same value c of the wave propagation speed.** (5) is in agreement with $p = h/\lambda$, in which, as the momentum of the photon increases, a shorter wavelength corresponds, which, based on (2) and (3), leads to a smaller significant size X and a smaller equivalent rotation period t , so that light speed remains constant.

Results

Michelson-Morley experiment led to conclude the aether as not existent. In reality, considering the vacuum as a fluid made up of IA bosons, each with speed $s=\pm 1h$, the condition that c must be constant still remains respected. Indeed, according to (5), regardless of the reference system, the speed of light depends on the ratio between the dimensions of the IAs the electromagnetic wave transits through and their equivalent rotation period t . The value of these variables depends on the momentum and energy possessed by the IAs owing to the electromagnetic wave transmitted through them. In relation to the experiment, in the outward journey of the light parallel to the "aether wind" it is assumed, for example, that the "aether wind" entails a hypothetical decrease in speed. In this case the photons have a lower momentum. According to (2), (3) and (5) the energy possessed by the IA boson is also lower, hence the increase of X and t in such a way that, as discussed above, their ratio $c=X/t$ remains constant. Conversely, it happens in the case when the light propagates with "aether wind" in favour, that is X and t decrease in such a way that their ratio still remains constant and equal to c . It is possible to make similar reasoning also for the perpendicular beams. What varies between beams traveling in different directions with respect to the "aether wind" is the frequency. By rotating the device, the photon beams change frequency between them, but they always travel at the same speed $c=X/t$. Moreover, in the last path before reaching the detector, beams travel parallel to each other, so they have same momentum and therefore same frequency. In intermediate positions, with photon beams that propagate in oblique directions with respect to the "aether wind", the trajectories can be decomposed in parallel and perpendicular directions to it.

Conclusions

The invariance of light speed and interference observed in Michelson-Morley experiment still remains verified even if it is assumed that the vacuum, within certain energy values, is actually a fluid consisting of a discrete number of IA bosons. All previous considerations, including the ones in Ref.1 and Ref.2, are made starting from the official experimental observations.

Notes

A less significant secondary polarizations are hypothetically conceivable.

B A single quantum of action involves two adjacent IAs (Ref. 1, 2). Each electric charge interacts with its opposite charge in the same IA, but it could also hypothetically interact with the other two charges of the adjacent IA.

C In the hypothetical stable unperturbed equilibrium condition all IA bosons have the same energy and momentum values E_0 and p_0 . In reality this condition is not reached owing to the background radiation and the space-time curvature (Ref. 1, 2).

D The energy state and thus the size of the IA bosons on planet Earth, where the experiments are conducted, will be different from energy state and dimensions of IAs located in very remote regions of space-time with low energy content. In particular the “ultimate equilibrium” frequency $f_* = 1,0638E+23$ 1/s is calculated from the stable unperturbed equilibrium condition (Ref.1, 2). In accelerator experiments the energy value required for the pair generation could also therefore be significantly different from 880MeV, corresponding to the energy at the “ultimate equilibrium” frequency (Ref. 1, 2).

Acknowledgements

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References

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